

THE NATURE OF LANGUAGE CHANGE**Kenjayeva Gavharshod Nurali qizi***English teacher of the 2nd professional school**Yangiyul district, Tashkent, Uzbekistan*aslgavharishoda97@mail.ru

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Annotation. The present article is devoted to the topic of language change and several factors which can be cause for this phenomenon. Especially changes are discussed according to two different kinds of motivations: internal and external. There are given some reasons for language change and results of this situation.

Key words: language change, internal motivation, external motivation, epiphenomenon, consciousness and attitude

Language change is a topic that must be included in any treatment of linguistics. Language evolution provides information on the nature of language. The explanations for why languages develop may provide insight into how people learn languages, how society uses language, and other topics. details about how it is structured internally. Language change cannot be explained in a straightforward manner. There is a lot of supposition and scant evidence in this subject. Although the field is intriguing and productive, there aren't many, if any, clear-cut solutions. Because of this, historical linguistics has generally focused on how languages change rather than why they do so in a certain way and not another. In this article we discuss some reasons of language change according to Hickey. Throughout the paper we explain and work on his ideas about the language change.

Why change happens. It is the first question to be asked before any linguist. The purpose of speakers is not to change the language. Instead, it is what is referred to as a “epiphenomenon” – something that occurs but is not planned. In terms of language, an epiphenomenon is a change that takes place for internal, external, or a combination of both reasons, but the change is not what the speakers intended. A

traffic jam, which emerges from every automobile braking to avoid colliding with the vehicle in front of it, illustrates the argument. However, no driver intentionally causes a jam; rather, it forms as a result of the traffic's compression as a result of stopping and resuming. As a result, the gridlock is an epiphenomenon brought on by the actions of the drivers.

Despite the lack of predictability, it is possible to see that some forces are present at various linguistic levels. These forces are in confrontation with one another, which causes some tension. The phonetic level of language favors simple syllable codas, as seen in the accompanying table. In fact, several languages, including unrelated ones in south-east Asia, exhibit an almost complete lack of clusters at the endings of words. If a language has a complicated morphology that involves ends on word stems, the phonetic tendency to shorten syllable codas might have serious repercussions if it became the norm among later generations of speakers.

The definition of language change can be seen from at least two different angles. From the standpoint of historical linguistics, a change is an innovation that occurs in a person's grammar but later spreads to the speech of other adults, but from the perspective of formal syntax, a change is the learning of distinct grammars across two or more generations of speakers [2:33-34]. It's also crucial to point out that, in the opinion of academics like Thomason, a change in the frequency of a certain element is likewise regarded as a change in the language.

It is also worth considering how language change can be studied. This problem can be approached from two different angles. That is, the study of language at one point in time, that is, the study of the synchronic aspect of language, and the study of the development of language over time, that is, diachronic study. However, neither of these two approaches can provide a complete picture of linguistic changes. Language can change mainly through two forces. These forces, individually or in combination, can bring about change.

One is language-internal pressures, such as similarity changes that occur when one element of a language is similar to another element of the same language. For

example, the Old English plural of cow was kine, but later became cow by modeling the common pluralization process of adding -s to the end of a noun [1: 442]. Another way language changes is influenced by the language you interact with. These changes are called contact-induced changes. However, sometimes the two forces combine to cause language change. These changes are thought to be due to several reasons [3: 62].

Internal and external motivation. Language shifts can basically be divided into two types. The changes refer to the structural aspects of the language. This is an internally motivated change. In this case, we are talking about changing external reasons. Internal Variation Internally induced variation usually results from system imbalances, removal of fixed elements, similar distributions in normal form, etc. That is, it ensures syntactic consistency. Because language is made up of different levels, a change in one term can cause an imbalance in another term, leading to another change. For example, changes in pronunciation can affect the shape of a language. In Old English, the case writing system disappeared as the endings faded away, and grammatical gender disappeared in Middle English. Existing language structures are important in stimulating or retarding change. It is assumed that there was an extrinsic motivation, there being no internal reason why these changes had to be initiated, as in Late Middle English.

Consciousness and attitudes. The extent to which speakers perceive language changes depends on the level of exposure. As expected, changes involving the closed class of the segment are not as conscious to the speaker as changes in the open class. A prime example of the latter type of change is lexical change. Ordinary speakers always use new words or expressions when talking about change. Traditionally, native speakers have considered language change as language decline. There could be two main reasons for this. One is the general desire for constancy that people exhibit. The second is the association of language change with social groups that commentators do not recognize, such as adults and teenagers or the working-class middle class. The tendency to stop language from changing and look back to find patterns in language that have not changed has given rise to notions of good and bad

in language. Correct use is immutable. Cast iron with clear and somewhat outdated rules. Misuse, on the other hand, is fluid, decadent, unregulated, and socially undesirable.

To sum up, for an objective study of language change, such a view is false. They, of course, have more to do with the people who use them and our attitudes towards them than with biased language itself. You can get used to small changes, but they can be annoying at first. In general, the first can be called strange, the second a little unusual, and the third completely normal.

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